

Inhibitory effects of the soil solution on radicle elongation of IR72, LTCCE and LTFE, IRRI.

into which plant residues have been incorporated after every harvest than in LTCCE plots from where residues have been removed. Thus, it is assumed that inhibitory substances in the chloroform fraction may be derived from plant residues.

The concentration of the test solution applied for bioassay was 20 times that of the original. Hence, it should be further confirmed whether the growth and yield of rice plants in LTCCE and LTFE plots are directly affected through root development by those substances under practical conditions. The chemical identification of the substances, especially in the chloro-

form fraction, is the subject of another study.

References

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Yield response of different rice varieties to root damage at the heading stage

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Root systems play an important role in the absorption and storage of water and nutrients and in the synthesis of certain hormones. Root cutting may increase the growth and yield of rice because the soil disturbance resulting from root cutting has some beneficial effect on soil conditions, or excess root production may reduce shoot growth because it competes for carbohydrates. Moreover, differences among soils, varieties, and management systems exist. To determine whether a large root system is beneficial to yield, we conducted a field experiment on the effect of root cutting at the heading stage in Guangzhou, China, in 1998. The soil was a clay loam, fertilized with 150 kg N, 33 kg P, and 124.5 kg K ha⁻¹. Five varieties were grown in the early-season and late-season experiments: Guang-Lu-Ai (short stalk) and Er-Qing-Ai (tall stalk) for the early season (March–July); Pei-Za 72 (hybrid rice), Feng-Ai Zhan 1, and Te-San-Ai for the late season (July–November).

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing at two seedlings hill⁻¹. The root systems of treated blocks were vertically cut 1 cm away from the stalk to a 20-cm depth on one, two, or three sides of the plant (T₁, T₂, T₃, respectively) at the heading stage. No cutting was done in the control variety (check). Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Block size was 15 m². Root activity was measured in terms of α-naphthylamine-oxidizing activities with a spectrometer. Yield and yield components were analyzed and recorded at maturity.

Table 1 shows that root cutting at the heading stage significantly increased root activity at the ripening stage in general, irrespective of varieties and treatments. The remaining roots evidently compensated for the ones removed.

In Table 2, one-side cutting (T₁) increased yield in four varieties (Guang-Lu-Ai, 10.2%; Pei-Za 72, 4.6%; Feng-Ai Zhan 1, 12.8%; and Te-San-Ai, 11.4%) and decreased yield in one (Er-Qing-Ai, 18.2%). The difference was mainly associated with a difference in grains panicle⁻¹ and percentage filled grains. Two-side cutting (T₂) and three-side cutting (T₃) caused

Table 1. Effect of root cutting at heading stage on root activity (μg α-NA g⁻¹ DW h⁻¹).

Treatment	Variety ^a				
	Guang-Lu-Ai	Er-Qing-Ai	Pei-Za 72	Feng-Ai Zhan I	Te-San-Ai
Check	43.7 b	87.5 b	96.4 c	59.2 b	84.2 b
T ₁	48.3 b	111.8 a	108.2 b	73.4 a	89.3 ab
T ₂	111.4 a	109.9 a	123.5 a	70.2 a	93.4 a
T ₃	101.7 a	102.3 a	109.5 b	68.4 a	90.5 a

^aNumbers followed by different letters in a column significantly differ at P = 0.05.

Table 2. Effect of root cutting at heading stage on yield and yield components of different rice varieties.^a

Variety	Treatment	Effective panicles (no. m ⁻²)	Grains per panicle (no.)	Filled grains (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield difference (%)
Guang-Lu-Ai	Check	300.0 a	90 a	86.4 a	25.9 a	6.0 b	0.0
	T ₁	312.5 a	94 a	88.9 a	25.5 a	6.6 a	10.2
	T ₂	282.5 b	95 a	88.5 a	25.8 a	6.1 b	1.4
	T ₃	292.5 b	94 a	87.0 a	25.4 a	6.1 b	0.6
Er-Qing-Ai	Check	270.0 a	155 a	85.1 a	23.8 a	8.5 a	0.0
	T ₁	260.0 a	143 b	78.0 b	23.9 a	6.9 b	-18.2
	T ₂	250.0 a	144 b	83.2 a	23.3 a	7.0 b	-17.7
	T ₃	270.0 a	133 c	84.2 a	24.3 a	7.4 b	-13.3
Pei-Za 72	Check	243.8 a	255 a	71.0 a	19.2 a	8.5 a	0.0
	T ₁	233.3 a	267 a	74.5 a	19.1 a	8.9 a	4.6
	T ₂	247.3 a	241 b	71.4 a	19.3 a	8.2 a	-3.1
	T ₃	225.0 b	234 b	66.7 b	19.2 a	6.7 b	-20.4
Feng-Ai Zhan I	Check	246.5 ab	214 a	63.1 b	20.6 a	6.8 a	0.0
	T ₁	247.3 ab	191 b	78.6 a	20.7 a	7.7 a	12.8
	T ₂	236.3 b	171 c	64.4 b	19.9 a	5.2 b	-24.5
	T ₃	267.8 a	189 b	52.9 c	20.2 a	5.4 b	-21.2
Te-San-Ai	Check	207.5 b	172 a	66.9 b	28.9 a	6.9 b	0.0
	T ₁	220.0 a	169 b	73.3 a	28.2 a	7.7 a	11.4
	T ₂	227.5 a	166 b	69.3 ab	28.4 a	7.4 ab	7.7
	T ₃	212.5 a	180 a	66.1 b	27.5 b	7.0 b	0.8

^aNumbers followed by different letters in a column in the same variety significantly differ at $P = 0.05$.

yield increases in two varieties (Guang-Lu-Ai, Te-San-Ai) and yield decreases in the others (Er-Qing-Ai, Pei-Za 72, Feng-Ai Zhan I).

It can be concluded that light root cutting at the heading stage has no significant effect on rice yield. It can even increase the yield of some varieties. This

may be because root cutting can increase root activity at maturity, which is important in absorbing water and nutrients and delaying plant senescence.

Equilibrium moisture content of rice and maize upon drying

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Cereal grain is ordinarily harvested at moisture contents above safe storage levels; therefore, additional drying is usually needed (Robayo and Pfof 1973). During drying, heat is necessary to evaporate moisture from the grain and a flow of air is needed to carry away the evaporated moisture (Trim and Robinson 1994).

The equilibrium moisture content (EMC) of cereal grain is important in both drying and storage because of its relationship with the relative humidity

(RH) and temperature of the air. Crop grains (including cereals) are hygroscopic and will lose or gain moisture until equilibrium is reached with the surrounding air (Henderson and Perry 1955, Trim and Robinson 1994).

This experiment observed the interaction between water and crop grain by measuring EMC as a function of RH at constant temperature. A plot of the equilibrium RH and moisture content (MC) is known as the moisture curve.

The drying experiment was conducted at RIMOC in Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, to study the equation/curve of EMC by using a mechanical batch-type dryer with a grain bin in a 5-m² (2 × 2.5 m) rectangular box, 0.9 m tall, and holding 1–1.5 t of rice or maize at a depth of 0.35 m. The drying air temperature and drying air velocity were 43 °C and 50 m³ min⁻¹, respectively.

Varieties IR42 (rice) and Bisma (maize) were used in this experiment. The